

Chondrocyte morphology on polymer-silica nanocomposites prepared by sol-gel technique

E. Costa Martínez, J.C. Rodríguez Hernández, J.L. Gómez Ribelles

M. Monleón Pradas, M. Salmerón Sánchez

Center for Biomaterials and Tissue Engineering, Technical University of Valencia

Camino de Vera s/n, 46022 Valencia, Spain

masalsan@fis.upv.es

SUMMARY

Polymer-silica nanocomposites based on poly(2-hydroxyethyl acrylate), PHEA, were prepared with different amounts of silica ranging from 5 to 30 wt.%. Chondrocyte adhesion and morphology was investigated as a function of the amount of silica in the system. Peculiar cell behaviour was shown to occur as the fraction of silica in the system increases.

Keywords: silica, PHEA, sol-gel process, chondrocyte, cell culture.

INTRODUCTION

Cell adhesion to synthetic materials is mediated by extracellular matrix proteins (including fibronectin (FN), laminin, and vitronectin) which adsorb on the substrate upon contact with physiological fluids *in vivo* or culture medium *in vitro* [1]. The concentration, distribution and mobility of the adsorbed protein layer on a surface play a fundamental role in the biofunctionality of a synthetic material and are clue factors to understand the biological response of a substrate. The (nano)incorporation of different amount of inorganic phase into a polymeric matrix is able to enhance the bioactivity of the substrate by, e.g., inducing the formation of an apatite layer but, on the other hand, on the short-time might influence drastically the initial cell-material behaviour, which modifies cell adhesion and morphology.

We have prepared polymer-silica nanocomposites based on poly(2-hydroxyethyl acrylate), PHEA, by the simultaneous polymerisation of the organic and the silica phases in a sol-gel process. Besides, we have performed *in vitro* chondrocyte culture on the different hybrids and the cell-material interaction was shown to depend strongly on the presence of silica in the system.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Samples were obtained by the simultaneous polymerization of 2-hydroxyethyl acrylate and TEOS (98%, Aldrich) as described in [2]. The silica content was changed from 5 to 30 wt% by controlling the HEA/TEOS ratio. The nanophase distribution within the different samples was characterised by differential scanning calorimeter and atomic force microscopy, including nanoindentation experiments.

Human articular cartilage from the knee of a patient undergoing total knee arthroplasty was processed for chondrocyte isolation as described in [3]. PHEA-SiO₂ films

presterilized with 25 kGy gamma radiation. Chondrocyte dispersion was placed onto the polymer films and was maintained at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere under 5% carbon dioxide for different times. The culture medium used was DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS and 50 mg/mL ascorbic acid, and it was renewed every 2–3 days. Cell morphology was observed by phase contrast microscopy on the different samples and viability assessed by neutral red vital staining.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The structure of PHEA/silica hybrid nanocomposites has been resolved by means of tapping mode AFM and nanoindentation experiments. Even though tapping mode AFM shows no qualitative difference as the amount of silica in the sample increases, nanoindentation experiments are able to correlate the tapping images with the structure of the inorganic phase. Therefore we may conclude that tapping mode AFM images are not sufficient to understand these hybrid system structures, and the use of nanoindentation allows one to gain a further insight into the structure. It is suggested that silica aggregates are isolated in the organic PHEA matrix up to 15 wt% silica in the sample. From this composition on, the silica phase becomes co-continuous with the organic matrix, what leads to a qualitative change in the stiffness of the samples. Scanning probe experiments are further supported by DSC experiments and a steep decrease of the amount of PHEA able to undergo the glass transition process takes place around 20 wt% silica content.

Cell behaviour changes dramatically as the amount of silica in the system increases. Cells are able to form clusters which attach weakly to the surface of the material. Nevertheless, cells are shown to be viable after 8 days on the material as neutral red staining reveals (Figure). Moreover, when these cells are collected from the nanocomposites and seeded again on a standard substrate acquire the typical fibroblast-like morphology. This peculiar cell-material interaction behaviour has interesting consequences for some applications including chondrocyte phenotype maintenance for tissue engineering techniques.

Figure. Chondrocytes on organic/inorganic nanocomposites. (a) after 10 culture days on TCPS after 4 days on the PHEA/SiO₂ 15% (CPLM, 100x). (b) Neutral red staining shows cell viability of cells on PHEA/ SiO₂ 5% after 8 days (CPLM, 200 x).

References

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